

LRP-OPTIMA: Optimized Layer-wise Relevance Propagation for Explaining Educational Recommendation Models

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Abstract

In the era of personalized educational recommendations, the interpretability of recommendation systems remains a critical challenge. This paper introduces an advanced framework, **Layer-wise Relevance Propagation with Optimized Parameter Thresholding and Integrated Model Analytics (LRP-OPTIMA)**, designed to generate explainable item recommendations in educational contexts. LRP-OPTIMA enhances traditional Layer-wise Relevance Propagation (LRP) by incorporating an error threshold parameter and integrating feature importance data from SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) and Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations (LIME). This method is implemented across diverse neural network architectures, including Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), and Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU), to prove its efficiency in providing transparent and interpretable recommendations. The relevance scores generated by LRP-OPTIMA are validated through stability analysis, statistical testing, and feature pruning analysis, offering deep insights into the role of input features in shaping recommendation outcomes. Visual heatmaps are employed to intuitively explain the decision-making process, thereby enhancing user trust and comprehension. Experimental results demonstrate the effectiveness of LRP-OPTIMA in improving both the transparency and interpretability of recommendation systems, particularly in educational applications where explainability is paramount.

Keywords: E-learning · MOOC · Layer-wise Relevance Propagation · Educational Recommendation System · Explainable Recommendation System

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Figure 1: **Relevance of Explainability in Education:**This diagram illustrates how explainability enhances the course recommendation process in an educational setting. A deep neural network recommendation engine (which is actually a blackbox) suggests a new course based on courses already completed by the student. To address the student’s question of ”Why is this course recommended?”, an interpretability tool provides a feature importance heatmap, which helps the student understand the recommendation, leading to improved clarity and trust in the system.

1 Introduction

Recently, recommendation systems have become ubiquitous in facilitating personalized user experiences across various domains such as education, e-commerce, entertainment, and social media. In the educational domain, recommendation systems are critical in guiding students toward courses that align with their learning needs and preferences. While these systems excel in predicting user choices, end-users, such as students, educators, and other stakeholders, still need to understand the underlying rationale behind their recommendations. Explainability is crucial for building trust in these systems and complying with regulatory requirements regarding transparency in automated decision-making processes [7].

Traditional recommendation models, often based on collaborative filtering or matrix factorization, lack explicit interpretability, making it challenging to justify why specific courses are recommended to students. This opacity can hinder the adoption and acceptance of recommendation systems in educational settings, where the ability to explain why a course is suggested is essential for fostering trust and supporting informed decision-making. To address this limitation, recent research has increasingly focused on employing interpretable machine learning techniques to shed light on the decision-making processes of recommendation systems. Fig. 1 illustrates the course recommendation process using a deep neural network in an educational context, emphasizing the role of interpretability in understanding why a particular course is recommended.

LRP [6] is an effective tool for interpreting neural networks. It assigns relevance scores to individual input features or neurons according to their impact on the model’s predictions. By tracing these relevance scores backward through the network layers, LRP helps identify which features are most influential in shaping the recommendation outcomes. In the context of educational recommendations, these features may include variables such as learner ID,

course ID, course average rating, course counts, instructor performance, sentiment score of learner comments, instructional level, language, and course category. Identifying the most influential factors in course selection is critical to optimizing the educational recommendation process.

This paper investigates the application of LRP-OPTIMA, an enhanced LRP-based method that incorporates an error threshold to regulate the propagation of relevance scores through the layers in the network. LRP optima also uses the feature importance information provided by existing model interpretability tools like SHAP [21] and LIME [26]. Integrating LIME and SHAP scores with LRP enhances the interpretability and robustness of the explanations by combining LIME's local (instance-specific) feature importance with SHAP's global (overall model behavior) perspective, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the model's predictions. This method is applied across several neural network architectures commonly used in recommendation systems: MLP, RNN, LSTM, and GRU. Each architecture offers unique advantages for capturing different aspects of student behavior and course characteristics, making them suitable candidates for comprehensive evaluation using LRP.

Furthermore, the relevance scores obtained from LRP are validated using statistical tests, stability analysis, feature-pruning analysis, and recommendation performance analysis, establishing a quantitative basis for interpreting feature importance in educational recommendation tasks. Heatmap visualizations illustrate the spatial distribution of relevance scores, enhancing the interpretability of the recommendation outcomes.

The contributions of this paper include:

- **Error Threshold for Relevance Propagation:** Introduces LRP-OPTIMA, which uses an error threshold to prevent incorrect predictions from skewing relevance scores, improving interpretability.
- **SHAP and LIME Integration:** Combines SHAP's overall model insights and LIME's specific instance details with LRP to provide a fuller picture of feature importance.
- **Rigorous Validation:** Validates relevance scores through statistical tests, stability analysis, and feature-pruning to ensure robustness and accuracy.
- **Heatmap Visualizations:** Uses heatmaps to visually represent relevance scores, enhancing the interpretability of recommendations.
- **Insights for MOOC Platforms:** Analyzes extensive MOOC datasets (COCO [10] and Xuetang¹) to highlight key features that can help MOOC platforms improve course recommendations and user engagement.

Through empirical evaluations, this research aims to demonstrate how LRP-OPTIMA can enhance the interpretability of educational recommendation systems, thereby fostering trust and acceptance among students, educators, and other stakeholders. Ultimately, the insights gained from this study contribute to advancing the field of explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) in personalized educational recommendations, ensuring that the factors influencing course selection are transparent and well-understood.

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2 Related Works

2.1 State-of-the-art in Educational Recommendation and Explainability

The integration of AI into educational systems continues to gain momentum, with recent studies focusing on its ability to enhance personalized learning, improve student outcomes, and support decision-making processes in various educational contexts.

Rane et al. [25] discussed the evolution of educational models with AI integration, emphasizing Education 4.0 and 5.0. They highlighted how AI-driven adaptive learning systems dynamically adjust instructional strategies based on real-time feedback, tailoring the learning experience to individual students' needs. The study also addressed ethical challenges in implementing these technologies at scale, advocating for AI systems that maintain engagement through personalized content recommendations.

Owan et al. [24] explored the application of large language models (LLMs) in educational assessment. Their study demonstrated how LLMs could analyze students' test results to provide targeted feedback and recommendations, aiding in identifying areas for improvement and reinforcing strengths.

Huang et al. [14] investigated the impact of AI-enabled personalized recommendations on student engagement in a flipped classroom setting. Their findings revealed that such recommendations significantly boosted students' learning performance and engagement with moderate motivation levels, especially when integrated into video-based learning modules.

Guleria et al. [12] focused on the role of machine learning and explainable AI (XAI) in educational data mining, particularly in career counseling. The study proposed a framework using ML models to analyze educational data, providing decision support for career planning. The ML models demonstrated high performance in predicting outcomes relevant to job placements and skill development.

Afzaal et al.[3] examined the use of explainable AI for supporting self-regulated learning. Their approach provided intelligent feedback and actionable recommendations, helping students to manage their learning processes better. Implementing this system, mainly through a dashboard interface, significantly enhanced student performance and self-regulation skills.

Ka'bi et al. [5] delve into applying deep learning techniques, such as CNN and LSTM, to develop recommendation models for higher education. Their proposed AI algorithm enhances students' cognitive capabilities by improving their ability to quickly locate, comprehend, and retain information. The algorithm outperforms traditional models like Gram-CF and FCNN-CF, emphasizing student self-esteem and overall mental quality.

Takami et al. [28] investigate the impact of explainable recommendations in an educational setting, specifically focusing on high school students' summer vacation assignments. The authors developed an explainable recommendation system based on Bayesian knowledge tracing models, which generates explanations for why specific quizzes are recommended. This system was employed to study how the presence of explanations influences student engagement. Crompton et al. [9] present a comprehensive overview of AI's role in online higher education, highlighting four key areas of application: predicting student performance, recommending learning resources, automating assessments, and enhancing the overall learning experience.

Afreen et al. [2] introduce LOXER, a learner-centered ontology designed to improve the explainability of educational recommendations. By integrating insights from various sources, including traditional educational datasets and learner feedback, LOXER fosters diverse decision-making processes and enhances the transparency and effectiveness of recommendations.

Takami et al. [29] investigated the impact of an explainable recommendation system using the Bayesian Knowledge Tracing model on middle school students' math performance. The system provided reasons for recommending specific quizzes, helping students better understand and engage with the material. The study found that students who interacted with the recommended quizzes improved their ability to solve previously challenging tasks, indicating that the system effectively supported learning. The study suggests that explainable recommendations can enhance academic performance by helping students overcome learning obstacles.

2.2 State-of-the-art in LRP-based Interpretability of Deep Learning Models

This section explores various techniques, adaptations, and applications of LRP, highlighting its significance in providing interpretability to complex models, particularly deep neural networks. The review aims to identify trends, gaps, and potential areas for further research by examining a broad range of studies. It comprehensively explains how LRP methods have evolved and their impact on improving model transparency and decision-making across different domains.

Li et al. [19] introduced a novel method known as the Feature-Level Spatial-Temporal Layer-Wise Relevance Propagation (ST-LRP). This approach enhances the traditional LRP by incorporating spatial and temporal dimensions, thereby improving both interpretability and prediction accuracy in building energy prediction tasks. The ST-LRP method provides a detailed explanation of how different input features correlate with energy consumption predictions. By considering both spatial and temporal factors, it quantitatively assesses the influence of multiple input features on the prediction results.

Li et al. [20] propose an advanced methodology for interpreting convolutional neural network (CNN)-based fault diagnosis models in Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) systems. The study introduces an improved Layer-wise Relevance Propagation (ImLRP) technique designed to enhance the interpretability of CNN models used in this context. To address the challenge of preserving both positive and negative information from HVAC inputs, the authors incorporate a Softsign activation function into the CNN architecture. Additionally, they tackle the feature-matching issue by omitting pooling layers from the network. ImLRP works by assigning relevance scores to each neuron across all layers during the back-propagation process, effectively evaluating each neuron's contribution to the final output decision. A novel metric, the relevance score difference, is introduced to quantify the net impact of HVAC faults, providing a clearer understanding of the model's diagnostic decisions. This approach represents a significant advancement in the interpretability of CNN-based models for HVAC fault diagnosis.

Guo et al. [13] introduce a novel approach to enhance the detection of generated texts

by utilizing a feature extraction method based on LRP. The proposed technique aims to improve the performance of feature mining, enabling more accurate identification of generated content. By leveraging LRP, the method provides deeper insights into the feature relevance within neural networks, making it a promising tool for detecting artificially generated texts with greater precision.

Wang et al. [31] present a novel approach to explainable audio classification by analyzing playing techniques through the use of LRP. Their study maps the audio signals into the carrier-modulation domain using a scattering transform, allowing for a detailed decomposition of neural network predictions. Their findings reveal that the most significant regions of interest are closely associated with the modulation rates of playing techniques independent of pitch. This work establishes a clear link between the neural network predictions and the physical characteristics of audio signals, offering entirely data-driven insights. The implications of their research extend to new possibilities in sound production and the analysis of music gestures.

Nam et al. [23] emphasize the importance of feature selection in EEG-based motor imagery (MI) classification, mainly due to the low signal-to-noise ratio inherent in EEG data, which can introduce irrelevant features that may negatively impact model performance. They apply a feature selection approach grounded in the LRP method to address this. This method, originally developed for dissecting trained neural networks in image classification, is employed to identify and retain only the most relevant EEG features For MI classification, thereby improving the accuracy and reliability of the models used.

Jung et al. [16] introduce a method for explaining the predictions of CNNs and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) through selective layer-wise relevance propagation. This approach enhances the clarity of the resulting heatmaps by integrating relevance-based and gradient-based methods, offering a more precise visualization of how these networks make decisions compared to existing techniques.

Mandloi et al. [22] present an explainable deep learning approach for brain tumor detection and classification, organized into four stages. The first stage uses a conditional generative adversarial network (cGAN) to create synthetic MRI images for various tumor classes, addressing issues of data imbalance and overfitting. The second stage involves detecting brain tumors with pre-trained models such as MobileNet, InceptionResNet, EfficientNet, and VGGNet. Upon detection, the third stage classifies the tumors using these models. In the final stage, LRP is applied to interpret the model's predictions, offering insights into the decision-making process.

Ullah et al. [30] explore the application of LRP to explain deep learning models For tabular data, specifically using an ID CNN architecture. Their study highlights the effectiveness of LRP at both the individual sample level and across the entire testing set. Additionally, they emphasize the significant computational efficiency of LRP, which requires only 1–2 seconds, compared to LIME (22 seconds) and SHAP (108 seconds) on the same hardware. This efficiency suggests that LRP could be particularly suitable For real-time application scenarios.

Cho et al. [8] proposed a GNN architecture in their study, Layer-wise Relevance Propagation of InteractionNet, designed to clarify protein-ligand interactions at the atomic level. Their method involves constructing two distinct graphs: one modeling intramolecular covalent bonds within the protein and ligand, and the other capturing intermolecular non-covalent

(NC) interactions between them. By using separate convolutional layers for covalent and NC interactions, this architecture provides multiple benefits. It enables the independent evaluation of each convolutional step’s impact on predicting dissociation constants and supports the exploration of graph construction strategies tailored to NC interactions.

Achtibat et al. [1] present a novel approach which addresses the limitations of existing XAI methods. Traditional local XAI methods generate attribution maps that highlight where important features are located but do not clarify what these features represent. In contrast, global explanation techniques visualize the general concepts a model has learned, offering insight into the overall model behavior but lacking specificity for individual predictions. The Concept Relevance Propagation (CRP) approach proposed in this work integrates both local and global perspectives, enabling a comprehensive understanding of individual predictions by answering both ”where” and ”what” questions.

Gautam et al. [11] employ multi-view clustering strategies to classify artifact images using Prototypical Relevance Propagation (PRP) explanations. This approach aims to mitigate the risk of artifact learning in models by effectively segregating these images.

Agarwal et al. [4] explore Explainable AI techniques for ML jet taggers in their study. They propose a method that boosts model interpretability by incorporating expert variables, known as ”eXpert-AUGmented” (XAUG) variables, into the input data. These XAUG variables are combined with intermediate layers and utilized in the final layers of the network. The study shows that XAUG variables enhance classifier interpretability, improve discrimination when combined with low-level features, and sometimes fully capture classifier behavior. LRP helps identify relevant information used by the network, and combining it with XAUG variables facilitates effective feature ranking and selection.

Lee et al. [18] present a new method called Relevance-weighted Class Activation Mapping (Relevance-CAM). This method uses LRP to weight components for generating explanation maps, addressing the shattered gradient problem common in gradient-based CAM methods. Relevance-CAM offers more accurate and robust visualizations of class-specific features from each layer of image processing models. The paper also introduces Contrastive Layer-wise Relevance Propagation (CLRP), which enhances LRP’s sensitivity to the target class by subtracting relevance scores of non-target classes, resulting in more precise heatmaps for the target class.

Xie et al. [32] tackle the challenge of explaining dynamic Graph Neural Networks (GNNs). Due to the time-varying nature of dynamic graph structures, conventional explanation models designed for static graphs are inadequate as they overlook temporal dependencies between snapshots. To address this issue, the authors introduce DGExplainer, a novel approach that provides reliable explanations for dynamic GNNs. DGExplainer works by redistributing the output activation scores of a dynamic GNN back through the network to the relevances of neurons in the previous layer. This iterative process continues until it yields the relevance scores for the input neurons, offering a comprehensive explanation of how dynamic GNNs make their predictions.

The findings are summarized in Table. 1.

Table 1: Summary of State-of-the-art in Explainability for Various Applications

Study	Application Area	Focus	Explainability Approach	Drawbacks
[19]	Energy Prediction	Spatial-Temporal LRP for building energy prediction	LRP with spatial-temporal factors	Misses out on global feature insights, counterfactual reasoning, and may not generalize to other types of models.
[20]	HVAC Fault Diagnosis	Interpretability for CNN in HVAC systems	Improved LRP with Softsign and relevance score difference	Misses out on global feature insights, counterfactual reasoning, and may not generalize to other types of models.
[13]	Generated Text Detection	Detecting generated texts with LRP	LRP-based feature extraction	Misses out on global feature insights, counterfactual reasoning, and may not generalize to other types of models.
[31]	Audio Classification	Explainable audio classification based on playing techniques	LRP in carrier-modulation domain	Misses out on global feature insights, counterfactual reasoning, and may not generalize to other types of models.
[23]	EEG-based Motor Imagery Classification	Feature selection for EEG data interpretation	LRP-based feature relevance analysis	Misses out on global feature insights, counterfactual reasoning, and may not generalize to other types of models.
[16]	CNN and RNN Interpretation	Selective LRP for CNN/RNN heatmaps	Relevance-based and gradient-based methods	Misses out on global feature insights, counterfactual reasoning, and may not generalize to other types of models.
[22]	Brain Tumor Detection and Classification	Explainable deep learning model with LRP	LRP for model decision transparency	Misses out on global feature insights, counterfactual reasoning, and may not generalize to other types of models.

[30]	Tabular Data Analysis	LRP application for ID CNN on tabular data	Efficient LRP computation	Misses out on global feature insights, counterfactual reasoning, and may not generalize to other types of models.
[8]	Protein-Ligand Interaction Prediction	GNN architecture with LRP for protein interactions	Layer-wise Relevance Propagation	Misses out on global feature insights, counterfactual reasoning, and may not generalize to other types of models.
[1]	Global and Local Explanation	Concept Relevance Propagation (CRP)	Combines local and global explainability	The effectiveness of CRP heavily depends on how concepts are defined, selected, and organized within the model.
[11]	Artifact Image Classification	Prototypical Relevance Propagation (PRP)	Multi-view clustering for artifact separation	If the artifacts are poorly defined, this approach might fail to separate genuine artifacts from class-relevant features.
[4]	ML Jet Tagger Interpretation	Explainable AI for jet tagging with expert variables	LRP with expert variables	Misses out on global feature insights, counterfactual reasoning, and may not generalize to other types of models.
[18]	Image Processing (Class Activation Mapping)	Relevance-weighted Class Activation Mapping (Relevance-CAM)	LRP and Contrastive LRP	Misses out on global feature insights, counterfactual reasoning, and may not generalize to other types of models.
[32]	Dynamic Graph Neural Networks	DGExplainer for dynamic GNNs	Relevance back-propagation	Redistributing activation scores to earlier layers may result in less precise attributions, as the relevance scores are spread across multiple temporal snapshots and layers.

3 Proposed System

The objective of this research is to develop a transparent and interpretable recommendation system using LRP. The system aims to predict course ratings based on learner characteristics (learner ID, course interactions) and course attributes (course ID, average rating for a course, total number of course enrollments, review polarity, course category, instructional level, and language of instruction). LRP will be implemented across various neural network architectures, including MLP, RNN, LSTM, and GRU, to analyze how effectively these architectures attribute relevance scores to input features and enhance model interpretability.

We utilize the COCO dataset , which provides comprehensive details about various courses, instructors, and evaluations for detailed analysis of the method. The dataset includes:

- **Courses:** Information on 43,113 courses, covering details such as short URL, short and long descriptions, objectives, requirements, language, first and second-level categories, instructional level, target audience, and subtitles.
- **Learners:** Data about 2,426,398 learners, including their completed courses, learner ratings, timestamps of learner-course interactions, comments, and review IDs.
- **Instructors:** Information on 16,963 instructors, detailing their job titles, total reviews, total enrollments, and the number of courses they have handled.

We predict the rating for a course concerning a learner applying the key features listed above using the neural network architectures - MLP, RNN, LSTM, and GRU. The predictions are explained using an improved Layer-wise Relevance Propagation (LRP-OPTIMA) method outlined below.

The general overview of the enhanced LRP with Error Threshold (LRP-ET) is given in Fig. 2. The overall process involved in LRP-OPTIMA for a general neural network architecture is given in Fig. 3 and is explained in detail below.

Calculating Normalized Prediction Error:

Normalized prediction error is computed using Eq. 1 to ensure relevance propagation only for samples with prediction errors less than a predefined threshold.

$$\delta_i = \frac{|y_i - \hat{y}_i|}{|y_i|} \quad (1)$$

where δ_i is the normalized prediction error for the i -th sample, y_i is the true value, and \hat{y}_i is the predicted value. If $\delta_i \geq 0.05$, the sample is excluded from the relevance propagation process due to excessive error. The samples with higher error rates are excluded from relevance calculation, so proper feature importance scores will be generated.

Initial Relevance Score Setting:

For MLP architectures, the relevance score for the i -th sample at the output layer is set using Eq. 2.

$$R^{(L)} = \begin{cases} f(x) & \text{if } \delta_i < 0.05 \\ \text{remove the sample} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Figure 2: **LRP-Enhanced with Error Threshold(LRP-ET)**:The figure illustrates the forward and backward passes in a neural network for Layer-wise Relevance Propagation (LRP). Input data is passed through the network during the forward pass, while relevance scores are back-propagated during the backward pass, conditioned on a normalized prediction error threshold. Only inputs with errors below the threshold contribute to the relevance computation. The formulas highlight how relevance scores are distributed across layers, with the resulting output heatmap visualizing feature importance.

where $R^{(L)}$ denotes the relevance score at the output layer and $f(x)$ is the model’s prediction for the input x .

For Recurrent architectures (RNN, LSTM, GRU), the relevance score at the final time step T is set using Eq. 3.

$$R^{(T)} = \begin{cases} f(x^{(1:T)}) & \text{if } \delta_i < 0.05 \\ \text{remove the sample} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $R^{(T)}$ denotes the relevance score at the final time step and $x^{(1:T)}$ represents the input sequence up to time step T .

Relevance Propagation:

Figure 3: Generic LRP-OPTIMA Process Flow Chart

Once the error threshold is satisfied, relevance scores are propagated backward through the network. The propagation method depends on the layer type:

The relevance is computed using Eq. 4 for fully connected layers.

$$R_j^{(l-1)} = \sum_i \frac{z_j^{(l-1)} w_{ij} + \epsilon \cdot \text{sign}(z_j^{(l-1)} w_{ij})}{\sum_i z_i^{(l-1)} w_{ij} + \epsilon} R_i^{(l)} \quad (4)$$

where $R_j^{(l-1)}$ denotes the relevance score for the j -th neuron in layer $l - 1$, $z_j^{(l-1)}$ is the activation of neuron j in layer $l - 1$, w_{ij} represents the weight from neuron i in layer l to neuron j in layer $l - 1$, and ϵ is a small constant to avoid division by zero.

For layers with non-linear activation functions, the derivative g' is included, and relevance propagation is defined by Eq. 5.

$$R_j^{(l-1)} = g' \left(z_j^{(l-1)} \right) \sum_i \frac{z_j^{(l-1)} w_{ij} + \epsilon \cdot \text{sign}(z_j^{(l-1)} w_{ij})}{\sum_i z_i^{(l-1)} w_{ij} + \epsilon} R_i^{(l)} \quad (5)$$

where $g' \left(z_j^{(l-1)} \right)$ is the derivative of the activation function at neuron j .

For RNNs, LSTMs, and GRUs, relevance is propagated through time steps and is given by Eq.6.

$$R_j^{(t-1)} = \sum_i \frac{h_j^{(t-1)} U_{ij} + \epsilon \cdot \text{sign}(h_j^{(t-1)} U_{ij})}{\sum_i h_i^{(t-1)} U_{ij} + \epsilon} R_i^{(t)} \quad (6)$$

where $R_j^{(t-1)}$ is the relevance score at time step $t - 1$, $h_j^{(t-1)}$ is the hidden state at time step $t - 1$, and U_{ij} denotes the weight connecting hidden states from time step $t - 1$ to t .

Continue relevance propagation until the relevance scores are obtained for the input layer (for MLP) or the initial time step (for RNNs, LSTMs, and GRUs).

Combining Relevance Scores:

To obtain overall interpretability score, the LRP-ET score is combined with SHAP and LIME values. The final LRP-OPTIMA score is computed by Eq. 7.

$$\text{LRP-OPTIMA}_i = \alpha \cdot R_i^{(0)} + \beta \cdot \text{SHAP}_i + \gamma \cdot \text{LIME}_i \quad (7)$$

where:

- $R_i^{(0)}$ is the final LRP score obtained at the input layer using LRP-ET.
- SHAP_i is the SHAP value for the i -th feature.
- LIME_i is the LIME value for the i -th feature.
- α , β , and γ are the weights assigned to each component, with the condition $\alpha + \beta + \gamma = 1$.

Grid Search Optimization:

To determine the optimal weights α , β , and γ , a grid search approach [15] was used. This method involves evaluating different weight combinations to minimize the model's mean squared error (MSE) generated using top-n features outputted by LRP-OPTIMA. Different values of n were also tested to find the optimal subset of features. The optimal weights found are:

- $\alpha = 0.4$
- $\beta = 0.35$
- $\gamma = 0.25$

These weights were selected as they provided the best balance in combining LRP-ET, SHAP, and LIME values for interpretability.

The model's predictions are explained by generating feature importance heatmaps, where the features' mean gradient values indicate each feature's contribution to a specific prediction. This information helps providers identify key focus areas in a MOOC environment, offering critical feedback to enhance course content and delivery.

LRP is highly advantageous for deep learning models, particularly complex architectures like LSTMs and GRUs. It directly works with a model's internal structure, propagating relevance scores backward from the output to the input layer, allowing for detailed feature contribution analysis. Unlike SHAP and LIME, which rely on approximations, LRP provides exact relevance scores using the model's weights and activation functions, ensuring accuracy. This makes LRP especially effective for sequential data, capturing contributions over time, and handling non-linearities within deep networks. LRP offers a consistent and reliable interpretation of the importance of features by aligning them with the model's training data and parameters.

LRP-OPTIMA, which integrates SHAP and LIME, offers detailed local and global explanations, preserving LRP's ability to analyze feature contributions across different layers while incorporating SHAP's consistent feature importance measures and LIME's model-agnostic applicability. LRP-OPTIMA improves trust and transparency, making it easier for users to understand model predictions, comply with regulatory requirements, and gain actionable insights for decision-making and model improvement.

4 Results

We conducted analysis on both the COCO and Xuetaang datasets. For qualitative evaluation, we focused on the COCO dataset due to its richer feature set. The hyperparameter tuning results on LSTM architecture is illustrated in Fig. 4 and is summarized in Table. 2.

Figure 4: Hyperparameter Tuning on LSTM Architecture

To benchmark the performance of our algorithm, we compared it against three established explainability methods: SHAP, LIME, and LRP. The evaluation was carried out using RMSE (Root Mean Squared Error) as the primary metric, providing a robust measure of prediction accuracy.

Table 2: Hyperparameters on LSTM Architecture

	LSTM Units	Activation Function	Optimizer	Learning Rate
SHAP	80	RELU	Adam	0.01
LIME	60	Leaky RELU	SDG	0.05
LRP	80	Leaky relu	RMSprop	0.05
LRP-ET	80	Sigmoid	RMSprop	0.001
LRP-OPTIMA	80	Tanh	Adam	0.01

Our work addresses three important research questions, which are listed below.

Table 3: **RMSE of Rating Prediction on Different Architectures**

#SAMPLES	MLP				RNN			
	2500	5000	7500	10000	2500	5000	7500	10000
RMSE	0.586	0.511	0.499	0.527	0.494	0.524	0.515	0.513
	LSTM				GRU			
	2500	5000	7500	10000	2500	5000	7500	10000
	0.499	0.519	0.496	0.533	0.530	0.514	0.502	0.527

- RQ1: How accurate are the predictions made by the recommendation architectures?
- RQ2: How to convert feature importance scores generated by LRP-OPTIMA into explanations?
- RQ3: How does LRP-OPTIMA enhance the interpretability and performance of neural network models?

4.1 RQ1: How accurate are the predictions made by the recommendation architectures?

The learner_rating was predicted for the test users with the help of the course, learner, and instructor features. The prediction algorithm was executed on the four different architectures. The RMSE values obtained are given in Table 3.

4.2 RQ2: How to convert feature importance scores generated by LRP-OPTIMA into explanations

The features used for predicting learner_ratings with their abbreviations used in this article are listed in Table 4. LRP-OPTIMA works as per the process explained in the 'Proposed System' section to generate feature importance scores. The deciding features for the predictions are explained with the help of heatmaps as given in Fig. 5, Fig.6, Fig. 7 and Fig. 8. The feature importance heatmaps show the gradient scores obtained for each feature under consideration for different sample sizes.

The average rank (based on feature importance) for each feature obtained by LRP-OPTIMA in the tested architectures was calculated as per Eq. 8. The overall rank over all the architectures is calculated as per Eq. 9. The results are summarized in Table 5.

$$\text{Rank}_{\text{architecture}}(f) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N r_i(f) \quad (8)$$

where N is the number of samples for that architecture and $r_i(f)$ is the rank of feature f in the i -th sample.

$$\text{Overall Rank}(f) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{j=1}^M \text{Rank}_j(f) \quad (9)$$

Table 4: Abbreviations Used

Feature name	Abbreviation
Learner ID	LID
Course ID	CID
Normalized Course Average Rating	NCAR
Normalised Course Count	NC
Normalised Instructor Performance	NIP
Sentiment Score	SS
Language	LA
Instructional Level	IL
Second Level Category	SLC

(a) #Samples: 2500

(b) #Samples: 5000

(c) #Samples: 7500

(d) #Samples: 10000

Figure 5: Feature Importance Heatmaps Generated by LRP-OPTIMA on MLP Architecture

Figure 6: Feature Importance Heatmaps Generated by LRP-OPTIMA on RNN Architecture

where M is the number of architectures and $\text{Rank}_j(f)$ is the consolidated score of feature f in the j -th architecture.

Table 5: Overall Feature Ranking

MLP		RNN		LSTM		GRU		OVERALL	
Feature	Rank	Feature	Rank	Feature	Rank	Feature	Rank	Feature	Rank
SS	2.0	SS	1.5	SS	1.25	SS	1.5	SS	1.56
NCAR	3.0	LA	3.0	NCAR	2.75	NCAR	2.0	NCAR	3.19
LA	4.25	NIP	3.75	LID	4.0	LID	3.5	LID	4.06
LID	4.5	LID	4.25	LA	5.0	LA	3.75	LA	4.00
NIP	4.75	NCAR	5.0	NC	4.75	IL	5.25	NIP	4.56
IL	5.75	IL	5.75	CID	5.75	NIP	5.25	IL	5.69
NC	6.5	CID	5.5	NIP	5.75	CID	6.25	CID	6.19
CID	7.25	NC	6.5	IL	6.0	NC	7.25	NC	6.44
SLC	7.5	SLC	9.0	SLC	9.0	SLC	9.0	SLC	8.63

The feature importance derived from LRP-OPTIMA for the course rating prediction model is in the order(highest to lowest): sentiment score, course average rating, learner ID, language, instructor performance, instructional level, course ID, course frequency, and course category. The justification for this ordering is:

- Sentiment Score: The most essential feature, as it directly reflects the learner’s feelings and opinions about the course, which strongly influences the rating.
- Course Average Rating: A key predictor since it aggregates past learner evaluations, providing a historical performance measure for the course.

Figure 7: Feature Importance Heatmaps Generated by LRP-OPTIMA on LSTM Architecture

- Learner ID: Important for capturing individual learner preferences and biases, which affect how they rate courses.
- Language: Influences ratings based on the language of course delivery, affecting comprehension and engagement.
- Instructor Performance: Significant as it directly impacts the quality of the learning experience and, consequently, the ratings.
- Instructional Level: Affects ratings by indicating the difficulty of the course content, which aligns with learner expectations and expertise.
- Course ID: Helps distinguish between courses but has less direct influence on ratings compared to other features.
- Course Frequency: Represents how often the course is offered, with a moderate impact on ratings due to factors like availability and updates.
- Course Category: The least influential, providing general classification but less directly related to the specific rating outcome.

These rankings highlight the relative impact of each feature on predicting course ratings, emphasizing the importance of learner sentiment and historical ratings, while contextual features and identifiers play supporting roles.

Figure 8: Feature Importance Heatmaps Generated by LRP-OPTIMA on GRU Architecture

4.3 RQ3: How does LRP-OPTIMA enhance the interpretability and performance of neural network models?

To assess the interpretability of LRP-OPTIMA, specifically whether the relevance scores attributed to various features are reliable, we conducted both feature pruning and stability analyses on the model.

Evaluating model performance through feature pruning:

We comprehensively evaluated model performance by calculating RMSE values across various architectures using the COCO and Xuetang datasets. Feature importance scores were determined through several methods, including LRP, LRP-ET, SHAP, LIME, and LRP-OPTIMA. To assess the effectiveness of these methods, we focused on the top seven features identified by each approach and re-evaluated the models based on these features.

The results reveal that LRP-OPTIMA, which integrates LRP with error thresholds and combines insights from SHAP and LIME, achieved notably lower RMSE values than other methods. This indicates that LRP-OPTIMA provides more precise feature importance scores and enhances the model’s overall performance. The improvement in RMSE values, as detailed in Table 6, Table 7, Fig. 9 and Fig. 10 underscores the robustness of LRP-OPTIMA in refining feature selection and boosting predictive accuracy.

Figure 9: Performance Comparison on COCO Dataset

In some cases, the RMSE may not decrease after feature pruning because the pruned features, while not essential, may still contain some valuable information for the model. Removing these features could result in a similar RMSE, as the remaining features capture most of the predictive power. Additionally, feature pruning helps reduce the model complexity and overfitting, leading to a more generalizable model, even if the RMSE does not decrease significantly.

Table 6: Model Performance (RMSE) on Selected Top Features Identified by Various Interpretability Tools on COCO Dataset

MLP				
#SAMPLES	2500	5000	7500	10000
SHAP [21]	0.486	0.511	0.498	0.520
LIME [26]	0.486	0.511	0.497	0.517
LRP [6]	0.512	0.511	0.497	0.518
LRP-ET	0.512	0.511	0.497	0.518
LRP-OPTIMA	0.512	0.511	0.497	0.517

RNN				
#SAMPLES	2500	5000	7500	10000
SHAP [21]	0.497	0.517	0.495	0.527
LIME [26]	0.497	0.558	0.605	0.533
LRP [6]	0.500	0.561	0.496	0.528
LRP-ET	0.494	0.523	0.499	0.530
LRP-OPTIMA	0.491	0.518	0.500	0.513

LSTM				
#SAMPLES	2500	5000	7500	10000
SHAP [21]	0.498	0.524	0.525	0.518
LIME [26]	0.501	0.510	0.498	0.528
LRP [6]	0.495	0.518	0.493	0.515
LRP-ET	0.503	0.518	0.493	0.517
LRP-OPTIMA	0.495	0.518	0.492	0.512

GRU				
#SAMPLES	2500	5000	7500	10000
SHAP [21]	0.495	0.514	0.498	0.517
LIME [26]	0.493	0.535	0.502	0.528
LRP [6]	0.493	0.514	0.493	0.524
LRP-ET	0.485	0.533	0.490	0.517
LRP-OPTIMA	0.489	0.510	0.496	0.519

Table 7: Model Performance (RMSE) on Selected Top Features Identified by Various Interpretability Tools on Xuetaang Dataset

MLP				
#SAMPLES	2500	5000	7500	10000
SHAP [21]	0.421	0.45	0.432	0.413
LIME [26]	0.3912	0.359	0.321	0.337
LRP [6]	0.491	0.443	0.448	0.482
LRP-ET	0.312	0.343	0.289	0.382
LRP-OPTIMA	0.321	0.208	0.2419	0.304

RNN				
#SAMPLES	2500	5000	7500	10000
SHAP [21]	0.920	0.980	0.97	0.91
LIME [26]	0.821	0.827	0.81	0.8
LRP [6]	0.6132	0.617	0.661	0.68
LRP-ET	0.745	0.799	0.764	0.6855
LRP-OPTIMA	0.6130	0.612	0.634	0.678

LSTM				
#SAMPLES	2500	5000	7500	10000
SHAP [21]	0.416	0.486	0.476	0.36
LIME [26]	0.376	0.319	0.268	0.240
LRP [6]	0.588	0.542	0.598	0.490
LRP-ET	0.511	0.553	0.545	0.462
LRP-OPTIMA	0.351	0.377	0.305	0.300

GRU				
#SAMPLES	2500	5000	7500	10000
SHAP [21]	0.76	0.528	0.645	0.624
LIME [26]	0.728	0.657	0.59	0.58
LRP [6]	0.612	0.566	0.517	0.559
LRP-ET	0.644	0.535	0.664	0.55
LRP-OPTIMA	0.492	0.50	0.575	0.421

Figure 10: Performance Comparison on Xuetang Dataset

Stability Analysis:

In addition to evaluating the performance of various interpretability tools through RMSE calculations, we conducted a stability analysis to assess the robustness of feature importance scores across different sample sizes (2500,5000,7500,10000). This analysis was performed using four distinct sample sizes, and the stability metrics included Average Kendall's Tau Correlation [17], Average Spearman's Rho [27], and Average Rank Variance.

Average Kendall's Tau Correlation:

$$\text{Average Kendall's Tau} = \frac{2}{N(N-1)} \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq N} \tau(r_i, r_j) \quad (10)$$

where N is the number of rankings and $\tau(r_i, r_j)$ is the Kendall's tau correlation between the i -th and j -th rankings.

Average Spearman's Rank Correlation:

$$\text{Average Spearman's Rho} = \frac{2}{N(N-1)} \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq N} \rho(r_i, r_j) \quad (11)$$

where $\rho(r_i, r_j)$ is the Spearman's rank correlation between the i -th and j -th rankings.

Average Rank Variance:

$$\text{Average Rank Variance} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{j=1}^M \text{Var}(R_j) \quad (12)$$

where M is the total number of features and $\text{Var}(R_j)$ is the variance of the ranks of feature j across all rankings.

The stability results, presented in Table 8, indicate that the Rank Variance was zero for MLP, LSTM, RNN, and GRU, suggesting that the feature importance rankings remained consistent across different sample sizes for these architectures. This stability ensures that the identified features consistently contribute to model predictions, regardless of the sample size.

The average Kendall's Tau correlation and average Spearman's Rho metrics demonstrated low values for MLP, indicating relatively less stability in feature importance scores for this architecture. In contrast, the metrics were notably higher for RNN, LSTM, and GRU, with GRU achieving the highest stability. This implies that the feature importance scores provided by these architectures are more reliable and less sensitive to sample size variations.

Overall, the stability analysis confirms that LRP-OPTIMA, mainly when applied to RNN, LSTM, and GRU models, offers a robust and consistent evaluation of feature importance, contributing to more reliable and interpretable recommendations across varying data samples.

Table 8: **Stability Analysis**

	MLP	RNN	LSTM	GRU
Average Kendall’s Tau Correlation	0.0370	0.3889	0.5463	0.5833
Average Spearman’s Rank Correlation	0.0444	0.4778	0.6083	0.6667
Average Rank Variance	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

4.4 Conclusion

Layer-wise Relevance Propagation with Optimized Parameter Thresholding and Integrated Model Analytics (LRP-OPTIMA) represents a significant leap forward in enhancing the interpretability of educational recommendation systems. By integrating the strengths of SHAP and LIME, LRP-OPTIMA offers a comprehensive, transparent, and user-friendly approach to deciphering the complex neural network models that power educational recommendations.

The necessity of explainability in educational recommendation systems cannot be overstated. Educators and learners alike need to trust and understand the recommendations provided, ensuring that decisions made by these systems are transparent and justifiable. The stability results underscore this by showing that the Rank Variance was zero for MLP, LSTM, RNN, and GRU architectures, which indicates consistent and reliable feature importance rankings across different sample sizes. This consistency ensures that the key features influencing recommendations are dependable and meaningful, regardless of the data used.

The higher stability of feature importance scores in RNN, LSTM, and GRU models, coupled with the strong positive correlation between actual and predicted values, as evidenced by Pearson correlation, reinforces the reliability of these architectures. Additionally, the statistical validation through T-test and Wilcoxon test confirms that the models’ predictions are closely aligned with actual outcomes, with no significant difference, thereby validating the accuracy and reliability of the recommendations.

In the educational context, where the stakes are high, and the need for personalized, fair, and transparent recommendations is critical, LRP-OPTIMA shines by providing robust, interpretable, and accurate insights into the decision-making processes of recommendation systems. This makes LRP-OPTIMA an indispensable tool for educators, data scientists, and other stakeholders, fostering trust and understanding in the recommendations that shape learners’ educational experiences.

5 Declarations and Data Availability Statement

- Financial interest: The authors declare no financial interests.
- Conflicts of interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.
- Informed consent: Since no human participation or animals are involved in this study, informed consent is not applicable.

- Data Availability: Data and code is available publicly at: <https://github.com/mehbooba/LRP-OPTIMA>

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